

MODERN METHODS IN THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES.

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Annotation: This article is about various innovative methods and their benefits for young people who are studying and mastering a foreign language in all regions, and studies the implementation of these methods by teachers using new technologies and the role and impact of the methods in the educational process.

Keywords: Innovation technologies, modern education, pedagogical activities of the younger generation, group games, conversation, educational facilities, effective methods.

Introduction: The current development of education gives rise to a new direction - innovative pedagogy. Innovative - from English means "introduction" (distribution). The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American researcher E. Rogers. He studied the classification of participants in the innovation process, their attitude to innovation, etc. In scientific areas, the concepts of innovation and innovation are distinguished. "Innovation" is a tool, a new method, methodology, technology, which means the same thing. "Innovation" is a process that develops in certain stages of education. The development of world science is booming and developing day by day. It is this positive development that has also had an impact on our world. Advanced innovative technologies are being introduced into our world of science.

It would not be wrong to say that the widespread introduction of advanced, modern innovative technologies into the field of education has also opened the door to wide opportunities and achievements for young people who are learning a foreign language.

Today, learning a foreign language requires a unique, unique spiritual and educational approach to organizing each lesson on the basis of a modern educational system and national heritage. The need to provide the educational process with modern pedagogical technologies is one of the conditions for implementing the "National Program for Personnel Training". It is a requirement of the time to provide young people studying in all educational institutions of our republic: preschool educational institutions, general secondary schools, vocational colleges, academic and higher educational institutions with modern pedagogical and information technologies, and to continuously organize their training with a new knowledge system. The role of advanced methods in allowing students to freely express their thoughts and to illuminate the topic in a group or team is of great importance. Therefore, the goals and objectives of teaching a foreign language and its methodology must correspond to and meet the interests of our society and the state, as well as the demands of the emerging younger generation. Foreign language teachers should correctly organize modern approaches to teaching foreign languages in foreign language lessons. They should know effective forms of implementing innovations in their pedagogical activities to improve their pedagogical skills

and professional competence in teaching a foreign language, technologies for creating didactic tools and electronic educational materials, and their use in the educational process will further improve the quality of students' learning of foreign languages. The use of group work also helps to develop such qualities as communication skills, mutual understanding, partnership, and a sense of mutual responsibility.

In addition, the use of new and effective methods for teaching a language, along with the expansion of the child's or student's worldview, helps to increase his or her ability to memorize and mentally develop in the new language he or she is learning. That is:

- When you say "To the left", you should look to the right,
- When you say "To the right", you should look to the left,
- When you hear "Up", you should look straight.

These and similar methods are very useful for the modern world and the children of the future. In the past, language learners considered this period to be a complex process and taught themselves that they had to go through difficult stages to master a language perfectly. However, now there are many modern language teaching methods, and one of them is the communicative, or conversational, method of language teaching. In this method, students improve their speaking and understanding skills together with their peers or another language learner. This method is the process of language teachers communicating through the language they are teaching and being able to convey what they are explaining to the student through this language. At the same time, this method is much more effective for language learners who have developed speaking skills and can explain their thoughts, even if only a little. That is, in this case, the language learner is able to quickly and easily convey his thoughts through monologues and dialogues.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that each foreign language has its own principles and stages of learning, and the process of mastering it can be somewhat difficult. Because in the process of learning a language, each person can compare its culture and vocabulary with their own, based on their own internal experiences. And at the same time, it is good to think like language users. But the methods that are currently emerging facilitate this situation and speed up the process of language learning. In recent years, new methods have been developed, and each of them has its own benefits for language learning.

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